

An Analysis of the Sex Offender Registry's Impact on Public Policy

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Abstract

In the United States, nearly every state requires that criminals who have committed sexual offenses to register in a public registry, along with sometimes requiring that the communities these offenders live in be notified of their crimes. The main law which requires public registration of sex offenders is often referred to as Megan's law. The laws requiring community notification are often separate but are normally seen under the umbrella of Megan's law. In this paper we will examine the societal impacts of these laws, including the cost of implementation and maintenance, along with the actual impact on offenders themselves including recidivism rates. We will also examine the political third-rail which maintaining a dissenting opinion towards the implementation of these laws has become, and the effect of this on the spread of the laws.

Keywords: Sex offender, Megan's law, Politics, Public Policy, Law Enforcement

A Primer on Megan's Law in New York

The implementation of the sex offender registry under Megan's law differs on a state-by-state basis; to get a basic view of the law, the implementation in the state of New York will be examined before discussing the law on a broader country-wide, multi-state level.

In New York, sex offenders are categorized as anybody convicted under a multitude of laws including everything from kidnapping children under seven, to rape. (*SEX OFFENDER REGISTRATION ACT*, 1996) Sex offenders after being found guilty are placed into one of three categories based on the severity of their crimes, as well as their likelihood of re-offending. (*SEX OFFENDER REGISTRATION ACT*, 1996) Based on their level, offenders have different responsibilities. For level 1, non-violent offenders, they are required to register on a mostly private registry accessible to law enforcement, every year for 20 years. Level 2 offenders, those which are violent and/or have a high probability of re-offending are required to register every year for life. Level 2 offenders can be downgraded and have the lifetime registration requirement waived. Level 3 offenders, those with the most serious crimes and/or with extremely high probability of re-offense are required to register every 90 days for their entire lives. (*SEX OFFENDER REGISTRATION ACT*, 1996).

Registered offenders of level 2 and 3 are publicly listed, their listing includes their home, work, and school addresses, their offense along with modus-operandi, and their level. Also included are any internet accounts, a photograph, and fingerprints. (*SEX OFFENDER REGISTRATION ACT*, 1996) The listing is online, and is nearly entirely publicly available, save a few minor pieces of data which are kept for law enforcement officials only, and may be released at their discretion.

In New York, it is left to the individual law enforcement agencies to decide if a community notification is required, but the state does regulate what and how information is released. (State of New York, 2019).

How Megan's Law Came to be

As is the case with nearly every law which is named after an individual, the origin of Megan's Law is not pleasant. Megan Kanka was a seven-year-old girl, who on July 29, 1994 was raped and murdered by her neighbor Jesse Timmendequas in New Jersey. ("Murder of Megan Kanka", 2019). Timmendequas was a convicted sex offender who was identified as violent, and highly likely to re-offend by medical professionals at the Adult Diagnostic and Treatment Center in Avenel, New Jersey. (Glaberson, 2019) Despite this risk, his neighbors were never warned about him which allowed him to get access to Megan Kanka easily.

After the murder of Megan Kanka, multiple bills were passed by the New Jersey General Assembly, which made the already existing sex offender registry public. (Mclarin, 2019) The goal of these laws was not to shame sex offenders as much as it was to make communities more cognizant of dangerous individuals in their area. It has often been noted that "community notification laws were enacted more to change the behaviors of potential victims than those of potential sexual recidivists." (Zgoba, Ph.D., Witt, Ph.D., Dalessandro, M.S.W. & Veysey, Ph.D., 2019) Meaning the laws were more created to make sure that potential victims had the knowledge needed to prevent victimization. This is an important distinction because as we will discuss later, the sex offender registry does little to improve recidivism rates.

The Political "Third-Rail" of Megan's Law

Based on the success Megan's Law as well as similar laws have had in getting passed, one would assume that the laws are not controversial, but this is not true at all. There are many challenges to the legality of such laws, specifically around double-jeopardy and personal rights. It is not, however, a popular position to be against these laws. Many politicians support these laws as those pushing it frame it as common-sense, and necessary to protect the children of the United States from a predator lurking in the shadows; and saying that one does not want to protect children is often a career-ender. When community notification laws were brought to the US House of Representatives, only one representative voiced opposition (Filler, D. M., 2001). When brought up for a vote "The provision initially passed the House 415 to 3, but the three opponents of the law-in an apparent search for political cover-changed their vote, resulting in a final tally of 418 to 0." (Filler, D. M., 2001). This profound support is not a great reflection of the debate and controversy surrounding the laws, but it is an excellent example of the fact that if you can frame a bill in the right way, it does not matter what a politician's personal belief is, they will support it to avoid the political and social ruin that would come as a result of voicing opposition.

As the law was not comfortable to debate it very quickly spread across the United States without much debate. The law passed in Virginia, Illinois, and Washington without a single "no" vote. (Filler, D. M., 2001) In the end, this law was enacted in the entirety of the United States, and in 2016 a law was signed which requires that the United States give advanced notice to foreign governments when certain sex offenders are traveling internationally from the United States. (Moody, 2019) This law continues to expand yearly in terms of the scope of the punishment levied. It is not only hard for politicians to speak out against, but it is easy for politicians to defend. The position "we need to keep children safe" is probably one of the most universally tenable positions ever.

Registration and Recidivism

One major misbelief is that Megan's Law has does anything to change recidivism rates of offenders. To start, sex offenses have a lower recidivism rate than compared to other offenses. The majority of recidivism of sex offenders are unrelated violent crimes, property offenses and probation or parole violations. (Iowa Office for Planning and Programming / Iowa Dept of Human Rights, 2019). Since the sex offender registry has been made public the recidivism rate for sex-offenses are at about 3 percent and unrelated offenses are at about 24.5 percent, before the registry was made public sex-offense recidivism was at 3.5 percent and unrelated offenses were at about 33.3 percent (Iowa Office for Planning and Programming / Iowa Dept of Human Rights, 2019). These differences are not statistically significant, and so the registry made no discernable difference in recidivism rates of sex-offenders. As was mentioned before however, the sex offender list can not be looked at as only having the goal of lowering sex offender recidivism rates, it also has the goal of changing the behaviors of potential victims around sex offenders.

Financial Impact of the Registry

The sex offender registry, like all things, costs money to setup and maintain. To start, the registry has an initial setup cost. When New Jersey setup their sex offender registry system, across 15 counties, the cost was around \$555,565. (Zgoba, Ph.D., Witt, Ph.D., Dalessandro, M.S.W. & Veysey, Ph.D., 2019) This cost comes from the establishment of a Megan's law group, online registry software, hardware, and other ancillary items.

To maintain the registry, those same 15 New Jersey counties spend somewhere around \$3,973,932 per year. (Zgoba, Ph.D., Witt, Ph.D., Dalessandro, M.S.W. & Veysey, Ph.D., 2019)

This includes the upkeep of the registry software and hardware, the salaries of staff, office space, and more. Maintaining this system is clearly an ongoing cost. One interesting thing to note is that the cost of running the system in New Jersey increased in cost in recent years, this is due to an expansion of the program to include things like GPS tracking of offenders. (Zgoba, Ph.D., Witt, Ph.D., Dalessandro, M.S.W. & Veysey, Ph.D., 2019) This leads to an interesting point; bureaucracies generally expand over time both in cost and scope. The reason this is interesting is the sex offender registration law is already a controversial law in terms of its impact on personal liberties, and any expansion of bureaucracies will impact offenders more, not to mention the increased cost.

Even with the high cost currently being spent on the sex offender list, it is far from perfect. Often entries are incomplete; in Kentucky for example, one study found that 43 percent of offenders had no photo, 8.2 percent had unknown addresses. Out of the addresses which were know, 10.5 percent turned out to be commercial locations, and 5.4 percent had addresses which simply did not exist. (Tewksbury, 2005)

Impact on Offenders

Few punishments reach the severity of sex offender registration in terms of intruding on an individual's life and removing liberties. Once offenders are registered their face is often plastered both on state sanctioned websites and sometimes even on physical flyers passed around their community. Given this publicity, offenders are often subject to extra-legal punishment by the community, either through the loss of friends, jobs, housing, or even physical attacks.

To understand what it is like for a sex offender on the list, one must look at the general experience reported by those individuals on the list. Sample data from Kentucky show that on

average, 42.7 percent of those on the list lost their job, 39.3 percent were treated rudely in public, 45.3 percent lost or were denied a place to live, and 54.7 percent lost a friend who found out about their registration. (Tewksbury, 2005) This means that likely most offenders on the list had at least one major impact on their life beyond a simple legal punishment.

While many people may be quick to write this de facto excommunication off as a just punishment for the crimes committed, it is important to remember that these individuals have already served time in prison and have been released to start rebuilding their lives. If offenders succeed with re-integration into society, there is a better chance that they will not re-offend. As one study asserted “The fear of exposure may cause offenders to avoid treatment, and in the case of pedophiles, may encourage offenders to seek out children as a result of adult isolation” (Zgoba, Ph.D., Witt, Ph.D., Dalessandro, M.S.W. & Veysey, Ph.D., 2019); meaning that the very law which is meant to protect children, may actually harm them in the long run, as offenders do not feel comfortable connecting with people who may shun them upon learning of their status, and they may even avoid seeking help for their condition because of the social stigma around it. Society has a stake in making sure that offenders are fully rehabilitated. Offenders who are carefully welcomed back into the community may build a stake in that community and become less likely to offend as they do not want to lose the place they have gained after losing it for a large amount of time. Commonly, it is reported that before re-offending, sex offenders felt “social withdrawal and heightened anxiety and stress” (Tewksbury, 2005); preventing those feelings is key to rehabilitating offenders who are capable of re-joining society.

Responsibility of Policy Makers

We have touched on some of the problems with the sex offender registry, and we have also explored the political minefield that Megan's Law and other legislation presents; now we will

look at possible fixes to the law. The law is not without both its merits and detractions. The law does allow communities to be aware of potentially dangerous individuals in their midst; the problem is, often offenders who will no re-offend, and have served their punishment are caught up in extreme version of public shaming.

Megan's Law and related legislation needs to be examined independently, but not completely removed, perhaps simply revamped now that data has been collected on the impact, both positive and negative of the law. Legislation is often emotional, but in treating this law as an emotional item society may be causing more harm than good. While not all sex offenders can be rehabilitated, legislation should work to aid those that can be in doing so, and successfully overcoming whatever challenges caused them to offend in the first place.

Legislatures should also ensure that they are voting with facts rather than only the knee-jerk feelings of society. Even though it is not the most comfortable place to be, and rationally a politician may suffer for doing so, sometimes dissenting to something is just the right thing to do even if it seems impossibly difficult.

Conclusion

The sex offender registry has both bad and good points. Using statistics, and personal accounts these laws can be revamped to ensure that those that need help are getting it, punishments are fair, and those that are surely a danger to society are kept under close watch. Megan's law is an excellent case study in emotional law making, and political third-rail topics. It is important that society learn how to speak openly and frankly about topics which are uncomfortable, as often that is where the most important legislation is needed.

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